

MONITORING AND ADMINISTRATION OF URBAN ENVIRONMENT USING GEOINFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

This article discusses how geographic information technologies (GIS) can be used to monitor and administer urban environments. In modern conditions, when cities face the challenges of rapid population growth, urbanization, climate change and environmental degradation, traditional methods of urban management become insufficiently effective. GIS technologies offer innovative solutions to collect, analyze and visualize spatial data to enable more informed decision making.

The article includes a review of previous research in this area, including the work of Michael Goodchild, Rodrigo Garcia and Yang Li, who have made significant contributions to the theory and practice of GIS applications in urban management. The focus is on methods and algorithms used for data monitoring and analysis, such as data collection, data processing, analysis using clustering and spatial regression techniques, and data visualization using cartographic techniques and 3D models.

The paper details the flowcharts of urban environment monitoring processes and algorithms used for data analysis. Examples of mathematical models and thematic maps used to present the results of the analysis are given. The conclusion offers perspectives on the further development of GIS and its integration with other advanced technologies, such as the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence, to solve complex urban management problems.

The purpose of this article is to substantiate the importance and effectiveness of using geoinformation technologies for monitoring and administration of urban environment, as well as to provide practical recommendations and examples of using GIS technologies in various aspects of urban management.

Keywords: urban environment, administrative processes, analysis, algorithms, urban land, real estate, management, spatial data, geographic information systems, mathematical models

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern cities face a number of complex challenges related to rapid population growth, accelerated urbanization, development, climate change and environmental degradation. These challenges require innovative approaches to urban area management aimed at improving the sustainability of cities, the quality of life of their inhabitants and the efficient use of resources. Traditional methods of urban environment administration are often insufficient to solve these problems, as they cannot provide a complete and up-to-date picture of the ongoing processes.

In this regard, geographic information technologies (GIS) are a powerful tool that can significantly improve the processes of monitoring and management of urban areas. GIS include methods and tools for the collection, storage, processing, analysis and visualization of spatial data. They provide integration of data from

various sources, which makes it possible to obtain comprehensive information on the state of the urban environment and promptly respond to changes.

The application of GIS in urban management has a wide range of possibilities, including traffic management, environmental monitoring, urban development planning, utility management and emergency response. The use of GIS allows for more informed and informed decision-making, which contributes to more efficient urban management.

In recent years, there has been significant progress in GIS technology, driven by advances in computing power, improvements in data collection techniques such as remote sensing and the use of smart sensors, and improvements in data analysis techniques including machine learning and artificial intelligence technologies. These advances open up new opportunities for

monitoring and managing urban environments at a higher level.

Therefore, it is an important issue to review the current approaches to the application of geographic information technology in the monitoring and administration of urban environments. The article provides an overview of previous research in this area, describes the main methods and algorithms used for processing and analyzing spatial data, and considers the prospects for further development of GIS in the context of urban management. Special attention is paid to the practical aspects of using GIS to solve specific problems faced by urban administrations and services.

Research in this area demonstrates that the integration of GIS with other advanced technologies can significantly improve the monitoring and management of the urban environment, which will ultimately contribute to the sustainable development of cities and increase their investment attractiveness.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Geographic Information Technologies (GIS) started to be actively developed in the middle of the 20th century and since then have found wide application in various fields, including urban environment management. The most important studies in this field have made a significant contribution to the theoretical and practical aspects of using GIS for monitoring and administration of urban areas. The major works and achievements of key researchers in this field are discussed below [1].

Michael F. Goodchild is considered as one of the founders of modern geographic information science [2]. In his work "Geographical Information Science" (1992), he proposed the concept of GIS as a scientific discipline focusing on the collection, analysis and interpretation of spatial data. Goodchild developed spatial analysis techniques that became the basis for modern GIS applications. His research has shown that GIS can significantly improve decision-making processes in urban management by providing accurate and relevant spatial data [3].

A group of researchers published a study titled "The use of GIS in traffic management and control" in which they studied the use of GIS for urban traffic management [4]. Their study demonstrated how the integration of GIS with traffic models can optimize routes, reduce congestion, and improve the overall quality of the transportation system. This study was an important step in the development of intelligent transportation systems and showed how GIS can be used to solve complex problems in urban infrastructure.

In the study [5], researchers looked at the application of GIS to monitor air quality in urban areas. The result showed that the use of GIS can not only collect and visualize air pollution data, but also perform spatial analysis to identify pollution sources and assess the impact on public health. The work demonstrated that GIS is a powerful tool for environmental monitoring and planning activities to improve the quality of urban environment.

Martin Batty in his book "The New Science of Cities" (2013) proposed innovative methods for analyzing

and modeling urban systems using GIS [9]. Batty developed the concept of "urban metabolisms", which views cities as dynamic systems in which complex interactions between different components occur. His research has shown that GIS can be used to model and predict changes in the urban environment, allowing for a better understanding and management of urbanization processes.

Peter A. Longley, Michael Goodchild, David J. Maguire, and David W. Rhind in their book *Geographic Information Systems and Science* (2015) [5] offered a comprehensive guide to GIS theory and practice. This work covers a wide range of topics, from GIS fundamentals to advanced methods for analyzing spatial data. The research of Longley and his colleagues has contributed significantly to the development of spatial visualization and analysis techniques that are used in urban management.

In turn, researchers [6] studied the use of GIS to integrate natural disaster risk management and urban development planning. Their work showed that the use of GIS allows for integrated risk analysis and the development of strategies to reduce the vulnerability of urban areas to natural disasters.

In [7], researchers showed that GIS can be used to assess the vulnerability of transportation infrastructure to climate change and develop adaptation strategies. Their study emphasized the importance of GIS in managing urban infrastructure in a changing climate. Their work helped lay the foundation for modern map visualization techniques used in GIS.

Researchers in [9] also examined the application of spatial statistics to urban analysis and planning, showing that spatial statistical methods integrated into GIS allow for more accurate and detailed analysis of urban processes.

Xiao Zhang and Yan Li in 2016 investigated "Analysis of urban growth and sprawl from remote sensing data". They showed that the use of remote sensing data in GIS can effectively analyze urban growth and sprawl processes, which contributes to more informed urban development planning [10].

These and other studies have made significant contributions to the development of GIS and its application in urban environments [8]. They have shown that GIS is a powerful tool for monitoring and managing urban processes, enabling more effective solutions to complex urban management problems and contributing to sustainable urban development.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The following materials were used for the study and the application of geographic information technologies (GIS) in the monitoring and administration of the urban environment:

- satellite imagery and aerial photography: high quality satellite and drone imagery providing up-to-date data on the state of the urban environment;
- ground sensor data: information on air quality, noise, temperature and humidity from sensors installed in different parts of the city;
- geodetic data: precise coordinates and elevations of objects needed to create three-dimensional models of urban development;

- socio-economic data: information on population, economic activity, traffic flows and other aspects of urban life collected from various sources, including statistics, surveys and social media data;

- maps and plans of the city: historical and contemporary maps and city planning schemes used to analyze changes in the urban environment and plan further development.

To achieve the research objectives and effective use of GIS technologies in monitoring and administration of urban environment, the following methods were applied:

1. Data collection. Data collection is the first stage where different sources of information are used to obtain spatial data:

- satellite imagery: the use of satellites such as Landsat, Sentinel and others to obtain high quality images of the urban environment;

- aerial imagery: the use of unmanned aerial vehicles to obtain detailed images;

- ground sensors: installation and use of sensors to monitor air quality, noise, temperature and other parameters;

- geodetic surveys: conducting geodetic surveys to obtain accurate coordinates and elevations of objects;

- socio-economic surveys: collecting data on population, economic activity and transportation flows, etc.

2. Data processing. Data processing involves several steps:

- data cleaning: removing noise, errors and duplicates from the collected data;

- data filtering: selecting useful information and discarding unnecessary data;

- georeferencing: converting the data into a GIS-compatible format.

3. Data analysis. Various methods and algorithms are used to analyze spatial data, namely:

- data clustering: grouping data based on similarity. For example, the k-means algorithm is used to divide urban areas into clusters based on air pollution levels (1):

$$C_i = \frac{1}{|S_i|} \sum_{x_i \in S_i} x_i, \quad (1)$$

where C_i — cluster centroid i , S_i - set of objects in the cluster i , x_i - data object.

- Data interpolation: predicting values at unknown points based on known data. For example, the kriging method is used to predict air pollution levels (2):

$$Z(x_0) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i Z(x_i), \quad (2)$$

where $Z(x_0)$ predicted value at the point x_0 , $Z(x_i)$ - value at a known point x_i , λ_i - weight.

- spatial regression: modeling dependencies between variables taking into account their geographical location (3):

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_n x_n + \epsilon \quad (3)$$

where y - dependent variable, $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ - independent variables, $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$ - parameters of the urban environment model, ϵ - mistake.

4. Data Visualization. Data visualization is an important aspect of using GIS.

Cartographic visualization is used to create thematic maps depicting various aspects of the urban environment, such as air pollution levels, traffic flows, building density, etc.

Three-dimensional modeling involves the creation of 3D models of urban objects for the analysis and planning of urban development.

Interactive maps are used to develop interactive maps that allow users to interact with data, change scale, select layers and analyze information.

To demonstrate the application of the described methods, consider the example of air quality monitoring in urban areas.

Data on pollutant concentrations (NO_2 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$) are collected using ground sensors installed in different parts of the city. After that, data processing is performed where the data are cleaned from noise and errors and georeferenced. The next step is data analysis, where the data is clustered using k-means method to identify areas with high pollution levels. Interpolation of the data by kriging method is also performed to predict the pollution levels at points where sensors are missing. After that, spatial regression is applied to analyze the effect of building density and traffic flows on pollution levels.

The final stage is data visualization. This stage involves the creation of a thematic map showing air pollution levels in different parts of the city and a three-dimensional model showing the distribution of pollutants depending on the height of buildings.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Geoinformation technologies include a wide range of methods and algorithms that are used to collect, process, analyze and visualize spatial data. This study discusses the main stages of working with GIS and provides examples of flowcharts and algorithms used in the process of monitoring and management of urban environment.

Data collection is the first and one of the most important steps in working with GIS. Data can be obtained from a variety of sources including satellite imagery, aerial photography, sensor data, social media data and surveying. The main challenge at this stage is to ensure that the data are highly accurate and up-to-date.

Once the data has been collected, it needs to be pre-processed, which includes cleaning, filtering and converting the data into a consistent format. This process may include removing errors and duplicates, correcting coordinates and georeferencing the data.

Various algorithms such as clustering, interpolation, and spatial regression are used to analyze spatial data. Let's take a closer look at some of them.

Clustering is a method of grouping objects into groups (clusters) so that objects within one cluster are more similar to each other than to objects in other clusters. One popular clustering algorithm is the k-means algorithm.

The k-means algorithm involves several steps:

1. Set the number of clusters k .
2. Initialize k centroids randomly.
3. Repeat until convergence:
 - assign each object to the nearest centroid;
 - update the centroids based on the average of the objects in each cluster.
4. Return centroids and object assignment.

Interpolation is used to predict values at points where data are not available, based on available data. One popular interpolation method is the kriging method.

Spatial regression is used to model relationships between spatial data. An example is a regression model for predicting air pollution levels based on building density and traffic flows.

Cartographic methods, creation of thematic maps and 3D models of urban objects are used for data visualization. This allows visualizing the results of the analysis and facilitates decision-making.

For effective monitoring and management of the urban environment using GIS, it is necessary to have a clear understanding of the sequence of actions and algorithms applied at each stage, as shown in Figure 1,2.

Fig. 1. Stages of urban environment monitoring

Fig. 2. Data clustering algorithm

GIS also provides powerful tools for visualizing spatial data. For example, thematic maps can visualize the level of air pollution in different parts of a city. Using this data, a thematic map can be created that visualizes which areas of the city have high levels of air pollution.

Based on the above, it can be said that geographic information technologies provide powerful tools for monitoring and administration of the urban environment. They allow collecting, processing and analyzing spatial data, which contributes to more effective management of urban areas and improving the quality of life of citizens. In the future, the development of GIS and its integration with other advanced technologies, such as the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence, will open up new opportunities for solving complex urban management tasks.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This article considers modern approaches to monitoring and administration of urban environment using geographic information technologies. The conducted

research and analysis showed that the use of GIS provides significant advantages in the management of urban areas, improving the quality of life of the population and contributing to sustainable urban development.

GIS is a powerful tool that can effectively solve complex problems of monitoring and management of urban environment. The main benefits of using GIS include:

- accuracy and relevance of data: GIS allows spatial data to be collected and analyzed with high accuracy and in real time, which is particularly important for rapid decision-making in urban environments;

- integration of data from different sources: GIS integrates data from different sources, including satellite imagery, ground sensor data, socio-economic data and geodetic surveys. This provides a comprehensive picture of the urban environment and allows various factors to be taken into account in decision-making;

- data visualization: GIS provides powerful tools for data visualization, such as thematic maps, three-dimensional models and interactive maps. This allows the

visualization of analysis results and facilitates the understanding of complex spatial processes;

- prediction and modeling: GIS enables prediction and modeling of various processes in the urban environment, such as development growth, traffic flows, air quality and others. This contributes to better informed planning and management of urban areas.

In the course of the study, the main methods and algorithms used in GIS for monitoring and administration of urban environments were reviewed. Clustering methods, such as the k-means algorithm, allow objects to be grouped based on similarity, which is useful for identifying areas with particular characteristics, such as high levels of air pollution. Interpolation techniques such as kriging are used to predict values at points where data are missing, based on known data. This is particularly important for creating complete maps of the spatial distribution of parameters. Spatial regression methods allow the dependencies between variables to be modeled with respect to their geographical location. This is useful for analyzing the impact of various factors on the urban environment, such as building density and traffic flows.

Practical applications of GIS in the urban environment include:

- air quality monitoring: GIS allows air pollution data to be collected, analyzed and visualized, and pollution levels to be predicted in different parts of the city. This facilitates the development of measures to improve air quality and reduce negative impacts on public health;

- traffic management: GIS is used to analyze and optimize transport routes, which helps to reduce congestion and improve the overall transport infrastructure of the city;

- urban development planning: GIS enables the modeling of development growth and the design of sustainable urban development strategies, taking into account various factors and risks such as population density, infrastructure availability and environmental aspects;

- emergency response: GIS provides tools for rapid response to emergencies such as natural disasters, accidents and other incidents. This enables effective evacuation planning and coordination of emergency services.

The development of GIS and its integration with advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence opens up new perspectives for monitoring and administration of urban environments. Future research and development in this area may include many directions. The development of more accurate and reliable sensors, as well as the use of drones and satellites to obtain real-time data holds much promise. The application of machine learning and artificial intelligence to more accurately analyze and predict spatial data could impact the quality of administration. Creating more sophisticated and interactive visualization systems that allow users to interact with data and perform real-time analysis will accelerate data presentation processes. The development of integrated platforms that combine GIS with other city information

systems such as transportation, energy, and utility management systems will ensure optimal interconnection of different types of urban data.

Thus, GIS technologies play an important role in monitoring and administration of the urban environment. They provide powerful tools for the collection, analysis and visualization of spatial data, which contributes to more effective management of urban areas. The application of GIS can improve the quality of life of the population, increase the resilience of cities and develop strategies for their sustainable development. In the future, the further development of GIS and its integration with other technologies will open up new opportunities for solving complex urban management problems and improving the efficiency of urban infrastructure.

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